

ORGANIZATION OF DAIRY PRODUCTS PRODUCTION BASED ON WASTE-FREE TECHNOLOGIES

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Relevance. Currently, plant and animal waste plays a large role in solving food, environmental and energy problems. They should be considered as additional sources of valuable substances of natural origin.

Waste is generated during transportation, storage and processing. The main industries associated with their formation are: agriculture, food and processing industry, public catering.

Purpose of the study. Study methods of waste-free technologies in the production of dairy products.

Among the wide variety of food products consumed by humans, milk and its products occupy an important place in human nutrition. Since ancient times, milk products have been especially valuable and healthy. Dairy products are useful for their protein, essential amino acids and carbohydrates for the development of the body, phosphorus, potassium, calcium, vitamins D, A and B12.

Milk is an obligatory and necessary food product, as it contains the most valuable and easily digestible proteins, fats, carbohydrates, and minerals. Milk protein contains essential amino acids such as lysine, valine, leucine, tryptophan, methionine, and arginine. Milk fat contains about 20 fatty acids. Carbohydrates are presented in the form of milk sugar (lactose).

A person should receive part of the daily milk intake in the form of fermented milk products (200 ml) (kefir, fermented baked milk, etc.). They have pronounced antibiotic properties, prevent putrefactive processes in the intestines, due to the displacement of putrefactive microflora by lactic acid bacteria, and also contain more vitamins B6, B12. Fermented milk products have a distinctive feature - they stimulate the secretion of digestive juices and bile, thereby improving digestion and are recommended for diseases of the gastrointestinal tract.

During the processing of dairy products from whole milk, secondary dairy raw materials are formed - skim milk, whey, buttermilk. Skim milk differs in chemical composition from whole milk practically only in the absence of fat.

Whey is a protein-carbohydrate raw material obtained in the production of cheese and cottage cheese. In terms of usefulness, it is even superior to milk, since the biological value of whey proteins (albumin, globulin) is higher than the biological value of casein. Whey contains antibiotic substances (nisin).

The buttermilk remaining after the production of oil differs little in composition from skim milk, but in its nutritional and healing properties it is in many ways superior to it.

The most valuable part of all types of secondary dairy raw materials is protein. Currently, the production of soluble food concentrates from skim milk has been organized: caseinates, caseites, coprecipitates. They contain 2.5 times more protein and 50 times less lactose than skim milk powder. They are used as additives in the production of sausages, meat, fish, bread and other baby food products.

We have accumulated extensive experience in whey processing. Organizations produce whey powder and condensed whey. Whey concentrates are used in the baking, confectionery, and meat industries. A wide range of whey and buttermilk drinks are produced. Milk sugar is obtained

by crystallizing lactose from a concentrated whey solution. This waste-free technology is planned to be introduced into the Sadaf sut dairy plant in the Kagan district of the Bukhara region.

Conclusions: Milk is one of the most consumed daily food products. Non-waste technologies help to save costs not only for dairy plants themselves, but they also help to develop such industries as bakeries, confectionery, and meat industries.

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